

MATHEMATICAL RELIGIONISM

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ABSTRACT

The ontology of mathematics and its relation to the description of scientific theories has been an increasingly relevant issue as scientific knowledge progress. With this, debates regarding the truth-value of mathematics have implications on its use in the explanation of physical phenomena, of which many philosophers holding a nominalist position concede to its indispensability. In this paper, I will argue three claims: (1) mathematical objects not true—as abstract objects *do not* exist, (2) mathematics is dispensable to scientific theories, and (3) the truth-value of mathematics is falsely perceived. Mathematically imbued scientific theories such as quantum field theory derive from scientific inquiries that specifically aim to approach aspects of the universe which can be explained by mathematics. Through conceptual analysis, the paper will incorporate a retrospective analysis of mathematically imbued theories, fictionalism, and Kuhnian analysis in order to develop a version of fictionalist anti-realism that emphasizes the religionist perspective in mathematics in empirical science today while maintaining the rejection of the existence of mathematical objects.

Keywords: *philosophy of mathematics, fictionalism, empirical science, instrumentalism, paradigms*

1. INTRODUCTION

In Eugene Wigner's 1959 New York lecture, "*The Unreasonable Effectiveness of Mathematics in the Natural Sciences*," the Physics Nobel laureate declared that the usefulness of mathematics in the sciences has no rational explanation; 'bordering on the mysterious,' he says.¹ Wigner has justified reasons for claiming so.

Time and time again, mathematical concepts have been developed within specific areas of the discipline, only to appear in other seemingly unrelated contexts bearing highly effective applications. Consider the case with the two-dimensional Radon transform — coined after mathematician John Radon, who introduced it in 1917 — defined as²:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{R}_{p, \tau} [f(x, y)] &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x, \tau + px) dx \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x, y) \delta[y - \tau + px] dy dx \\ &\equiv U_{p, \tau},\end{aligned}$$

Where p is the slope of a line, τ is its intercept, and $\delta(x)$ is the delta function. Its inverse, where H is a Hilbert transform, is³:

$$f(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{d}{dy} H[U_{p, y - px}] dp$$

This integral transform, a method transforming a function from its initial space to another via integration, allowing for easier characterization and manipulation of certain properties of the original function in the new function space, measures the integrated value of a function along lines in a

¹ Wigner, Eugene P. "The Unreasonable Effectiveness of Mathematics in the Natural Sciences. Richard Courant Lecture in Mathematical Sciences Delivered at New York University, May 11, 1959." *Communications on Pure and Applied Mathematics* 13, no. 1 (1960): 1-14.

² Deans, S. R. *The Radon Transform and Some of Its Applications*. New York: Wiley, 1983.

³ Nievergelt, Y. "Elementary Inversion of Radon's Transform." *SIAM Rev.* 28, 79-84, 1986.

given direction. Radon wanted to address problems related to the mathematical representation of functions and to provide a means of characterizing and studying them. He was particularly interested in understanding how functions could be represented and analyzed in terms of their integrals along straight lines.

However, the transform's significance from expanded significantly when it found practical applications, particularly in the field of medical imaging. The Radon transform now plays a crucial role in computed tomography (CT) scans, being used to reconstruct images of internal structures based on X-ray measurements taken along different paths through the body.

The case of the Radon transform is not isolated. In the early 1800s, mathematician Évariste Galois developed group theory with the specific goal of addressing the solvability of polynomial equations. Groups, broadly defined as algebraic structures governed by specific rules, became a powerful tool in 20th-century physics, particularly in categorizing elementary particles—the fundamental constituents of matter.⁴ The expansion of the utilization of mathematical concepts to oftentimes unreasonable degrees and seemingly unrelated contexts⁵, along with its elegance and capacity to accurately describe physical phenomena, has not only fascinated thinkers such as Wigner, but has resulted in a general view of mathematics which can only be described as *religionist*.

Why *religionism*? What warrants the usage of the term? Religionism has a working definition in itself, “exaggerated religious zealotry.” This definition relates to how the term will be utilized in mathematical religionism, which I

⁴ Tung, Wu-Ki. *Group Theory in Physics: An Introduction to Symmetry Principles, Group Representations, and Special Functions in Classical and Quantum Physics*. August 1985. Michigan State University, USA. DOI: 10.1142/0097.

⁵ Additional instances that further demonstrate this characteristic include: Pascal’s triangle, the arrangement of binomial coefficients, which proved to be vital to the interpretation of NMR spectroscopy data; and the constant π , its appearances ranging from circular geometry, Heisenberg’s uncertainty principle, Fourier series, to the DNA structure and population dynamics tracking.

define as the position which asserts that “people, regardless of their relationship with mathematics, generally absolves the field of scrutiny with regards to its truth value, due to its intricate link to sciences, leading to unfounded ontological commitment.” This attitude towards mathematics is akin to religious zealotry, wherein established and enforced authority of religious dogma leads to little and vilified scrutiny towards the truth value of said dogma—faith stems from the complete acceptance of beliefs as unquestionable truth—hence the usage of the term for analogy’s sake.

Other philosophers may object to the coinage of such a term. However, those who do are free to refuse to acknowledge mathematical religionism as a genuine philosophical concept, so long as they are able to contest the need to concretize this attitude. If somehow, you do agree with the classification but find the term used to be misleading or misaligned, then feel free to use another word which you find more suitable and accurate.

Debates on the ontology of mathematical objects are essential to the philosophy of mathematics, either concerned with explanations as to how human beings have knowledge of such non-spatiotemporal objects which exist in an abstract world, or with the denial of its existence entirely. Its implications in the description of physical phenomena extend the debates into the *in*/dispensability of mathematics in the natural sciences, of which many philosophers holding a nominalist position concede to its ‘indispensability.’ However, I postulate that there needs to be further extensive discussions on the perception of mathematics as generated by its role in empirical science and unreasonable effectiveness, which will be done through a Kuhnian analysis of mathematics as paradigmatic.

In this paper, I will develop a version of fictionalist anti-realism, termed *mathematical religionism*, a single philosophical position which operates through three connected, central claims: (1) as per fictionalism, mathematical objects are not true as abstract objects do not exist, therefore mathematical sentences are false; (2) mathematics is not indispensable to empirical science; and (3) the truth-value of mathematics is falsely perceived and is paradigmatic in nature. These claims all justify the bifurcation of mathematics from science. In order to support the unique claim (3) that such

a false perception exists which should otherwise be modified, I must first prove that mathematics is fundamentally false and does not stand on an empirical ground, rather a psychological projection, ergo dispensable; thus, necessitating claims (1) and (2). The ultimate aim of this essay is to detach mathematics from its empirical authority in order to proportionately calibrate both the academe and the general public's perceptions to its actual truth value. Its urgency is rooted in the increasing mathematization of natural sciences, especially in quantum mechanics; physical phenomena which are incredibly convoluted and seemingly defy known laws of physics are being described with complex mathematical concepts in an attempt to make sense of them. Not only does this approach obscure modern science from the general public, with issues on science communication beginning to worsen⁶, it also exacerbates the limitations of mathematics as a scientific tool. Skepticism is in order. Lastly, practicing mathematicians often do not consider the philosophical questions which accompany the discipline, and if ever they do, do so in a contradictory, back-and-forth manner.

Before proceeding further, clarifications must be made regarding the scope of the paper and definition of terms. I will discuss the explanatory role of mathematics only within the realm of empirical sciences such as physics, biology, and chemistry—operationally, *empirical* refers to which is concerned with or is verifiable through evidence of the senses, by observation or experimentation. This excludes formal sciences, such as theoretical computer science, statistics, and cryptography, which are concerned with generating knowledge through formal systems. Empirical science is *a posteriori*, whereas formal science is *a priori*.

Furthermore, I am relieved of the burden of providing a unique, nominalistically accepted alternative system to mathematics. Correspondent to claim (2), Hartry Field's nominalization project will be demonstrated merely supporting the response to the Quine-Putnam indispensability argument. *Dispensability* is defined in this paper as eliminability which retains

⁶ 'Post-truth' and information anarchy has allowed for unverified 'scientific' information to prevail; issues such as mystification, compromised accuracy, lack of scrutiny, and cargo cult science plague empirical science today. (see Bucchi, 2019)

the attractiveness of the scientific theory. Attractiveness requires clarity, simplicity, unificatory power, generality, and fecundity.⁷ An element within a theory can be considered eliminable when an alternative theory exists that is empirically identical to the original, yet does not involve quantification over that specific element. Also, for a statement to be *true*, it must be describing something which has a pure basis in reality—that is the condition for truth.

Additionally, the stated burden would be more appropriate were the case of the paper be to claim that the role of mathematics is interchangeable with alternative systems. However, I argue that mathematics as a framework, is not the end-all-be-all of empirical sciences—the role which it plays does not warrant a foundational position in the hierarchy of scientific tools, given that these fields are, when bare, conceptual. Mathematics is at best supplementary to its operation.

Unreasonable effectiveness, as coined by Wigner, refers to the unusual and seemingly disproportionate ability of abstract mathematical concepts to accurately describe and predict empirical phenomena of the natural world. This is an essential characteristic of mathematics which leads to the religionist view.

2. HOW DID WE GET HERE?

2.1. *On Mathematicians (not) Caring*

What philosophers think about mathematics do not seem to matter much to practicing mathematicians. It's impossible to discern someone's philosophical stance—be it fictionalism, rationalism, Platonism, realism, operationalism, logicism, formalism, structuralism, nominalism, or intuitionism—solely from their engagement with mathematics. The general distance between the fields of mathematics and the philosophy of mathematics allows mathematicians the privilege of arguing for one philosophical position, then jumping to another. The challenge lies in the fact

⁷ Szabó, Máté. "On Field's Nominalization of Physical Theories." *Magyar Filozofiai Szemle* 54, no. 4 (2010): 231-239.

that, from a mathematician's perspective, philosophers pose inquiries that do not influence mathematical procedures.⁸ Although prior to the bulk of the arguments of this paper itself will be the review of related literature, most of which argue on issues which do not influence the practice of mathematics, the unique case of *religionism* which will succeed them posits more proximity to mathematical and scientific practice. French mathematician Jean Dieudonné observes of Nicolas Bourbaki that,

*On foundations we believe in the reality of mathematics, but of course when philosophers attack us with their paradoxes we rush to hide behind formalism and say, "Mathematics is just a combination of meaningless symbols," and then we bring out Chapters 1 and 2 on set theory. Finally we are left in peace to go back to our mathematics and do it as we have always done, with the feeling each mathematician has that he is working with something real. This sensation is probably an illusion, but is very convenient. That is Bourbaki's attitude toward foundations.*⁹

Dieudonné simply acknowledges this as a widely acknowledged reality within the contemporary mathematical world: A prevailing condition where most mathematicians coexist with two conflicting perspectives regarding the essence and significance of their endeavors. Reuben Hersh's question arises: Can we truly believe that this inherent tension does not leave any impact on the self-assurance and self-worth of individuals who, above all else, are expected to harbor a disdain for contradiction?¹⁰

Hersh examines this contradiction in *Some Proposals for Reviving the Philosophy of Mathematics*. The existence of mathematics as a unified profession, along with its capacity to collectively recognize certain mathematical accomplishments as worthy of the highest praise and reward,

⁸ Cheng, Eugenia. "Mathematics, Morally." Department of Pure Mathematics, University of Cambridge, January 2004.

⁹ Dieudonné, Jean. "The Work of Nicholas Bourbaki." *American Mathematical Monthly* 77 (1970): 134-145.

¹⁰ Hersh, Reuben. "Some Proposals for Reviving the Philosophy of Mathematics." *Advances in Mathematics* 31 (1979): 31-50. Department of Mathematics, University of New Mexico, Albuquerque, New Mexico 87131.

underscores the existence of common standards of excellence that serve as benchmarks for evaluating mathematical work. Articulating these criteria, bringing them into open discourse for examination, challenge, and debate, represents a significant philosophical undertaking for mathematicians, and the inability to sustain such a public discussion on mathematical values reflects a lack of philosophical awareness and proficiency to Hersh.

The issues of truth and meaning are not confined to technicalities within obscure branches of logic or set theory; they confront anyone engaged in the use or teaching of mathematics. While it is possible to overlook these matters, doing so would mean being confined by unexamined philosophical preconceptions. It would be surprising if such oversight did not have practical consequences. Such consequences, Hersh exemplifies, include critiques of the introduction of formalism in high schools have predominantly focused on pedagogical concerns, asserting that it is either the wrong content or the wrong instructional approach. However, he responds that these arguments lack conclusiveness when they fail to scrutinize the underlying assumption that authentic mathematics exclusively involves formal derivations from explicitly stated axioms. If this philosophical doctrine remains unexamined, those opposing formalism in educational settings may be perceived as endorsing a compromise in educational rigor. They could be viewed as pedagogical opportunists advocating for a diminished version of the "real thing" to be presented to students.

2.2. *Mathematics and the General Public*

There is no doubt that many people regard mathematics unfavorably. This perception has led to a negatively significant impact on mathematical education, among which are a relatively low interest in the subject in schools and the phenomenon of *math-phobia*—intimidation and aversion from, and a fear of mathematics—with both inadvertently affecting the academic performance of students.¹¹

¹¹ Begg, Andy. "Rethinking the Image of Mathematics." *Public Understanding of Mathematics and Mathematics Education*. ICME 10, DG7: Copenhagen, Denmark, 2004.

The average educator or researcher within the discipline seldom engages with the philosophical or epistemological dimensions of the discipline.¹² Individuals drawn to mathematics often find its allure rooted in its apparent dependence on logic and reason, presenting a realm seemingly immune to subjective opinion or interpretation. The research mathematician, in particular, finds motivation not only in the logical structure but also in the aesthetic aspects of mathematics, its inherent beauty and elegance, as well as recognizing the significance and relevance of their academic pursuits.

A proficient student of math derives pleasure from the subject, partly attributed to the absence of reliance on rote memorization, as the entire framework can be deduced from fundamental principles. The satisfaction of problem-solving, coupled with the ability to rigorously prove the correctness of solutions, enhances the academic experience. Nevertheless, these very students may experience a disconcerting sensation when confronted with instances of logical paradoxes. Similar unease arises when encountering abstract concepts like different infinities¹³, potentially unsettling their otherwise robust confidence in the certainties of mathematics.

¹² Jagadeeshan, Shashidhar. "The Nature of Mathematics - an Unfolding Story." *Journal of the Krishnamurti Schools*, no. 9 (2005).

¹³ Talking about infinity (∞) in a mathematical sense—some infinities are bigger than others. For instance, in set theory, Georg Cantor developed a system of transfinite numbers, which begins with aleph-null ($\aleph_0$), the cardinality of the set of natural numbers. Cantor revealed that the cardinality of the continuum, denoted as c , surpasses that of the natural numbers $\aleph_0$. In essence, he demonstrated that the set of real numbers ($\mathbb{R}$) is larger than the set of natural numbers, through $c = 2^{\aleph_0} > \aleph_0$, or aleph-one ($\aleph_1$).

In 1901, a contentious paradox was discovered that would shake set theory to its core. Bertrand Russell found that a set comprising all sets not belonging to themselves leads to logical inconsistency. This paradox, now commonly known as Russell's paradox, arises when considering scenarios such as a group of barbers who only shave men that do not shave themselves. If there exists a barber in this group who doesn't shave himself, according to the definition, he must shave himself. However, no barber in the collection can logically shave himself, thus creating a contradiction. In symbols:

$$\text{Let } R = \{x | x \notin x\}, \text{ then } R \in R \iff R \notin R.$$

Whether or not an average person is fond of the subject, one conclusion can be drawn as to how mathematics is generally perceived: *a logically sound, consistent, and intimidating discipline which plays an essential role in countless theoretical and practical fields, especially in the sciences*. This can be exemplified through a 2007 study conducted in the Rural Midwest in the United States by David M. Lucas and Jamie Fuggitt.¹⁴ They found that, regardless of age, most interviewees believed in the importance of mathematics and the need to study it even if the respondent did not like math as a subject.

The problem which arises from this perception, which in turn is exacerbated by aforementioned issues in math education, is the conflation of importance and soundness with ‘truth.’

How can a layperson question the nature of mathematics when: first, they do not have the sufficient skills and knowledge, and second, mathematics is *too* logical and objective to be false? Not only that, but even mathematicians and enthusiasts do not care to engage with its philosophical dimensions— who are we then, who hold no authority nor expertise, to scrutinize?

3. THOSE WHO HAVE THOUGHT ABOUT IT

It does not mean that, because the majority of practicing mathematicians take philosophical positions for granted, only focusing on doing math, academics have yet to tackle its epistemological and ontological issues. Philosophers exist; and what philosophers do best in regard to meddling with the affairs of other academic disciplines is doing the clean-up jobs, addressing what practicing experts cannot as they are limited by their field’s methodologies. Zoologists, for example, can’t necessarily tackle the ethical considerations of experimenting on live animals using the scientific method alone. Questions posed by these fields which are impossible to deal with

¹⁴ Lucas, David M., and Fuggitt, Jamir. "The Perception of Math and Math Education in the Rural Midwest." *Appalachian Collaborative Center for Learning, Assessment, and Instruction in Mathematics*, no. 37, May 2007.

through their theoretical frameworks alone necessitate philosophizing in order to be confronted.

I must provide an overview of the relevant philosophical debates surrounding the ontology of mathematical objects and the discipline's (in)dispensability in the description of physical phenomena, in order to set the stage for the proceeding arguments. Numerous positions have been developed beginning in the 20th century and dragging onto the present.

3.1. *Platonism*

Mathematical platonism has largely lost support from many philosophers during the turn of the century. This is due to the emergence of alternative, non-platonist positions on mathematical objects and their existence, among which are instrumentalist and nominalist. However, understanding the case of platonism is essential in forming responses to it and seeing how the Quine-Putnam indispensability argument arises from this metaphysical.

The main premise of platonism is that mathematical objects, which are abstract objects, exist because abstract objects exist. These objects exist independent of us and our thoughts and language, just as elementary particles do. Therefore, mathematical sentences state discovered—as opposed to invented—truths about these abstract objects.

Gottlob Frege presents a crucial argument affirming the existence of abstract mathematical entities.¹⁵ According to this viewpoint, the language of mathematics claims to reference and quantify over these abstract objects, and numerous mathematical theorems are acknowledged as true. For a sentence to be true, its sub-expressions must effectively achieve their intended references or quantifications. Thus, abstract mathematical objects must exist as denoted and quantified by these expressions.

Frege's argument relies on two key premises, the first of which pertains to the semantics of mathematical language:

¹⁵ Frege, Gottlob. *Foundations of Arithmetic*. Translated by J.L. Austin. Oxford: Blackwell, 1953.

1. *Classical Semantics*

The singular terms in the language of mathematics assert references to mathematical objects, while its first-order quantifiers claim to encompass such objects.

In this context, the term ‘purport’ signifies that for a sentence to be true, it must successfully achieve the specified referencing or quantifying.

The second premise, requiring less elucidation, is:

2. *Truth*

The majority of sentences accepted as mathematical theorems are true (irrespective of their syntactic and semantic structures).

Consider sentences acknowledged as mathematical theorems containing mathematical singular terms. According to the Truth premise, most of these sentences are true.¹⁶ Let S be one such sentence. By Classical Semantics, the truth of S necessitates the successful referencing of mathematical objects by its singular terms. Therefore, the assertion of Existence holds — there must be mathematical objects.¹⁷

¹⁶ The provided step involves the use of *parenthetical precisification* in the context of the Truth premise. Without this clarification, there is a potential ambiguity where, without specific constraints, most sentences acknowledged as mathematical theorems could be true, while all sentences following a particular form mentioned in the text might be false. Consider a mathematical system where the majority of theorems involve specific types of equations, say quadratic equations. Without precision, the statement could mean that most quadratic equations are true theorems. However, this might not hold for another type of mathematical statement, such as those involving higher-order polynomials. In this case, all statements of the form "higher-order polynomial equations are theorems" might be false, potentially leading to a contradiction.

¹⁷ There exists a parallel argument analogous to the Fregean one, pertaining to object-directed intentional act (*see* Gödel 1964). This argument posits that individuals possess intuitions about mathematical objects, and these intuitions are considered veridical. The premises of this argument lead to the conclusion of the existence of mathematical objects, as a veridical intuition necessitates the existence of its intentional object. However, the primary focus of this discussion (3.1) remains on the original Fregean argument, as it is deemed more manageable.

Continuing, I spare you the headache of scrutinizing every objection that has been presented to the platonist argument in favor of providing objections which are most relevant to the direction of my claims, most of which will serve as supporting, connected viewpoints. After all, the bulk of these objections and responses to these objections make up the majority of the philosophy of mathematics—I must avoid an exegetical approach at all costs.

3.2. *The Indispensability Argument*

Naturally, given the significant role mathematics plays in empirical science, it is inevitable that this relationship will be explored with regards to ontology, here specifically with the platonist (or realist) view. The appeal of empirical science does come from its rigorous a posteriori framework purely grounded in reality; a repertoire of knowledge which can be observed, replicated, and tested. It is humanity's best attempt at getting close to its idea of an objective truth. There is intrigue in the applicability, versatility, and effectiveness of mathematics in the sciences.

Logician Willard Van Orman Quine and mathematician Hilary Putnam, both philosophers of the analytic tradition, would eventually develop what is seen as the most influential indispensability argument in the discipline. The argument attempts to justify beliefs in the existence of mathematical entities and the indispensability of mathematics only so far as science is concerned. The argument is structured as follows:¹⁸

1. Our commitment to entities in ontology should include solely those entities indispensable to our most robust scientific theories.
2. Mathematical entities play an indispensable role in our most robust scientific theories.
3. (C) Therefore, we ought to encompass mathematical entities to our ontological commitment.

Assessing the truth of a mathematical sentence is considered more tenable than determining the accuracy of a mathematical intuition.

¹⁸ "The Indispensability Argument in the Philosophy of Mathematics." *Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. <https://iep.utm.edu/indimath/#H3>.

The foundational premise establishes a bedrock principle of ontological commitment, stipulating that the acknowledgment of entities within a specific domain should be confined to those deemed indispensable to our best scientific theories. Ontological commitment involves the conscientious recognition and acceptance of the existence of entities within a designated realm—in that, only the language has to commit to reference to the existence of these objects; they do not necessarily have to be physically real. Subsequently, the second premise emphasizes the significance of mathematical entities and their indispensable role in shaping scientific theories. This, however, is less self-evident than the first premise.

The term *indispensable* not only denotes utility but underscores the absolute necessity of these mathematical entities for the coherence and explanatory efficacy of our scientific frameworks. Oppositely, *dispensability* has been previously defined as eliminability which retains the attractiveness of the scientific theory, of which there are criteria set harkening to standard desiderata for good scientific theories.

The deduction logically emanates from these premises, positing that, given the indispensable role of mathematical entities in our most robust scientific theories, it is judicious to broaden our ontological commitment to encompass these mathematical entities. In essence, the recognition of the existence of mathematical entities aligns with the foundational principle of ontological commitment elucidated in the initial premise.

Because the argument only accounts for mathematics which serves the needs of empirical science and nothing more, naturally, we may ask—how much mathematics carries ontological commitment? What Quine says of this is that:

Magnitudes in excess of such demands, e.g., $\aleph_\omega$ or inaccessible numbers, I look upon only as mathematical recreation and without ontological rights. Sets

*that are compatible with $V = L$ ¹⁹ in the sense of Gödel's monograph afford a convenient cut-off.*²⁰

From Quine's perspective, pure mathematics plays a crucial role in our understanding of the world, wherein it is primarily focused on its application in empirical science. He sees the extensions, which are mathematical concepts that exceed the needs of application, as a simple way of enhancing our comprehension. In his work, Quine draws parallels with irrational numbers, where precision exceeds measurement requirements, and he illustrates how this process extends to higher set theory. Indenumerable infinities are acknowledged only because they are imposed by the simplest systematizations of more essential concepts. He ultimately suggests that these bridges, which are recreation at best, while not bearing any ontological rights, are essential to those which do.

3.3. *Objections to the Platonists*

In summary, among the many views which oppose the assertions of mathematical platonism, both the Fregean and Quine-Putnam arguments for realism, are the following:

1. Paul Benacerraf's influential objection of mathematical platonism²¹ is hinged on these three premises:
 - a. Mathematicians exhibit reliability, meaning that nearly every mathematical statement, S , accepted by mathematicians is deemed true.
 - b. To justify belief in mathematics, it must be theoretically possible to account for this reliability.
 - c. However, if mathematical platonism holds true, such reliability cannot be explained, even in principle.

¹⁹ Written as $V = L$, the constructability axiom, a potential axiom to set theory, states that all sets are constructible. Originating from Kurt Gödel's investigations, this axiom contradicts the proposition of the existence of zero sharp ($0^\sharp$) and more robust large cardinal axioms.

²⁰ See Quine 1986, p. 400

²¹ Benacerraf, Paul. "Mathematical Truth." *Journal of Philosophy* 70, no. 19 (1973): 661–679.

It then follows, if the premises are correct, that platonism impairs our justification for our belief in mathematics.

2. Hartry Field's project against the indispensability argument²² has been enjoying much of the limelight in the contemporary debates within the philosophy of mathematics.

He presents a pragmatic stance: he proposes that science does not necessarily rely on mathematics. Field contends that the utility of mathematical theories lies in their conservativeness rather than their truth-value; as long as they do not introduce new consequences beyond the nominalist scientific theory alone, they prove valuable. This clarifies how mathematics can find application in empirical science, although it doesn't address why it is employed. The latter is attributed to mathematics simplifying calculations and the expression of different theories.

The other aspect of his project is a demonstration of the nominalization of empirical science's best theories, of which there have been debates surrounding the likelihood of its success.

3. Penelope Maddy challenges the idea that we should have ontological commitment to *all* entities indispensable to our best scientific theories.²³ Her objections revolve around the difficulties in reconciling

²² Field, Hartry. *Science without Numbers*. 2nd ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198777915.001.0001>.

²³ Maddy, Penelope. "Physicalistic Platonism." In *Physicalism in Mathematics*, edited by A.D. Irvine, 259–289. Dordrecht: Kluwer, 1990.

—. "Indispensability and Practice." *Journal of Philosophy* 89, no. 6 (1992): 275–289.

—. "Naturalism and Ontology." *Philosophia Mathematica* 3, no. 3 (1995): 248–270.

naturalism²⁴ with confirmational holism²⁵, particularly in explaining the legitimacy of certain scientific and mathematical practices.

Maddy argues that scientists' attitudes towards components of well-confirmed theories vary, and naturalism suggests siding with the scientists who may not believe in all posited entities. She also questions the role of mathematics in scientific theories, suggesting that confirmational holism conflicts with actual scientific practice and, therefore, with naturalism. Maddy also argues that assessing new mathematical axioms should consider their coherence with current scientific theories, which contradicts standard mathematical practice and, in her view, conflicts with naturalism. These objections collectively undermine the support for the first premise of the indispensability argument—which if correct, renders Field “irrelevant” to the debates.

4. THREE CENTRAL CLAIMS

4.1. *First Claim: Fictionalism*

We first visit a challenge for set-theoretic platonism.²⁶ This is to initially illustrate (and in turn, *emphasize*) the ontological holes of subscribing to the belief that mathematical sentences are true descriptions of abstract objects—under a consistent, functioning mathematical morality,²⁷ if you will. This also debunks the claim that even you might be thinking of: that mathematical

²⁴ Naturalism is a philosophical doctrine asserting that there is no distinct first philosophy. Quine contends that philosophy does not hold a position of precedence or privilege over science; instead, it is considered an integral and continuous part of the scientific enterprise. (see Quine 1981)

²⁵ Confirmational holism posits that theories are validated or refuted as complete entities. Simply put, if empirical evidence supports a theory, the entirety of the theory is affirmed.

²⁶ Benacerraf, Paul. "What Numbers Could Not Be." In *Philosophy of Mathematics: Selected Readings*, edited by Paul Benacerraf and Hilary Putnam, 272–294. 1983.

²⁷ Mathematical morality is how mathematics should behave. (see Cheng 2004)

statements and theories pertain to ordinary physical entities, not abstract ones.

Benacerraf, who seems to be the archnemesis of mathematical platonism, illustrates two (of infinite other) ways in which we can identify natural numbers through utilizing pure sets. The two accounts are:

I.

$$0 = \emptyset$$

$$1 = \{\emptyset\}$$

$$2 = \{\{\emptyset\}\}$$

$$3 = \{\{\{\emptyset\}\}\}$$

⋮

II.

$$0 = \emptyset$$

$$1 = \{\emptyset\}$$

$$2 = \{\emptyset, \{\emptyset\}\}$$

$$3 = \{\emptyset, \{\emptyset\}, \{\emptyset, \{\emptyset\}\}\}$$

⋮

Benacerraf poses a straightforward question: *which account, I or II, exclusively comprises true identity statements?* Answering this proves complex. Establishing successor functions, addition, and multiplication operations on the number-candidates of both I and II allows for consistent arithmetical truths. However, divergence emerges when posing extra-arithmetical queries such as '1 ∈ 3?'—the two accounts yield conflicting answers. The impossibility of both accounts being correct is evident when examining the differing representations of 3: I as $3 = \{\{\{\emptyset\}\}\}$ and II as $3 = \{\emptyset, \{\emptyset\}, \{\emptyset, \{\emptyset\}\}\}$. This discrepancy violates the transitivity of identity, leading to a set-theoretic falsehood. This quandary, often termed Benacerraf's *identification problem*, underscores a paradox: neither account appears superior, yet they cannot coexist as true simultaneously. Such as that properties of physical objects cannot be paradoxical—an apple remains red; that specific apple cannot be red and green at the same time.

Paradoxes and loopholes weaken the case for the sustainment of ontological commitment in mathematics in the description of physical phenomena, making instrumentalism a much more attractive approach to how we perceive and use math. Physicalist views on math simply cannot account for these paradoxes, nor can it account for infinities or numbers which are too large to exist in our physical universe. Mathematical sentences *do* pertain to mathematical objects; it just so happens that some of these can be represented by real objects, being quasi-realist.

Thus, borne the FIRST OF THE CENTRAL CLAIMS: as per fictionalism, mathematical objects are not true as abstract objects do not exist, therefore mathematical sentences are false. Let us take this step-by-step.

The core of the fictionalist argument involves attempting to eliminate every alternative to fictionalism. The argument, as structured similarly to the *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* article²⁸, can be articulated as follows:

1. Mathematical sentences such as '3 is the square root of 9' should be taken literally, making straightforward assertions about specific objects. For example, '3 is the square root of 9' should be interpreted as a direct claim about the nature of the number 3. However,
2. If we interpret statements like '3 is the square root of 9' literally and assume their truth, it implies the existence of the objects they refer to. For instance, if '3 is the square root of 9' straightforwardly describes the nature of the number 3 and is true, then the number 4 must genuinely exist. Therefore, combining (1) and (2), we conclude that
3. If statements like '3 is the square root of 9' are true, it implies the existence of mathematical objects. Yet,
4. If mathematical objects exist, they are abstract entities, devoid of spatiotemporal properties. For instance, if the number 3 exists, it is an abstract object, distinct from physical or mental entities. However,

²⁸ Balaguer, Mark. "Fictionalism in the Philosophy of Mathematics." *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. Stanford University, July 23, 2018. Last modified July 23, 2018. <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/fictionalism-mathematics/>.

5. Abstract objects do not exist. Consequently, through *modus tollens* applied to (4) and (5), we deduce that
6. Mathematical objects, being abstract, do not exist. Consequently, through *modus tollens* applied to (3) and (6), we infer that
7. (C) Statements like '3 is the square root of 9' are not true (and not true for the reasons provided by fictionalists), thereby supporting the truth of fictionalism.

We clearly posit that for a statement to be true, they must be descriptions of the nature of objects and/or events which exist and if an event in spacetime, has happened. The rejection of the existence of abstract objects thus arrives at the radical conclusion that mathematics is fundamentally false, operating under fictions deemed necessary. It then follows that contrary to the Quine-Putnam argument, we do not have a responsibility to commit to mathematical objects ontologically.

One might argue that mathematical objects, while not abstract, are *mental* objects, as if math is a human invention, then surely, we can safely assume that mathematizing, which occurs within the human mind, implies that the objects which it describes and toy with exist within the confines of this organ, *right?* Wrong.

I return to infinities to refute this view swiftly. The human mind cannot possibly account for every single natural number, much less real numbers. True to mathematical theories, there are an infinite, uncountable number of mathematical objects. Every number, every operator, and every symbol are objects with unique properties consistent to axioms. How we mentally conceptualize such large quantities are through blobs; vague ideations of abstract objects which are enough to utilize these objects to do math using our heads.

In response, an alternative stance could involve asserting that mathematical claims concern ideas that we could *potentially* construct or hypothetical mental entities. However, adopting this perspective wouldn't align with the previously described view. In this view, the entities of mathematics wouldn't be actual mental objects but rather potential objects,

likely falling into the category of abstract entities or other metaphysically uncertain types. Psychologism therefore should not be merited.

4.2. *Second Claim: Dispensability*

After arriving at the conclusion that mathematical sentences are fundamentally false due to mathematical entities not existing, it would be reasonable to then claim that mathematics is dispensable to scientific theories.

Quine and Putnam argued that the indispensability of mathematics to empirical science is good reason to subscribe to the belief of its existence. However, I assert that we do not have any sort of ontological commitment to lend to mathematical objects, even if we entertain the premise of indispensability being a condition for ontological commitment, per P1 of the Quine-Putnam argument. I will now defend the SECOND OF THE CENTRAL CLAIMS: that mathematics is not indispensable to empirical science.

First, in response to Quine's caveat that inaccessible numbers and excessive magnitudes in mathematics do not bear any ontological rights and are merely recreational—the distinction between accessible and inaccessible numbers to determine the extent of ontological rights is purely arbitrary and should not hold any logical weight.

Quine's claim that only accessible numbers bear ontological rights presupposes a restrictive view of the mathematical landscape and contradicts the history of mathematics and science. Mathematical structures often exhibit a remarkable degree of universality, as we have previously seen. Irrational numbers and certain infinite sets, for instance, often play crucial roles in mathematical theories that are highly applicable to the description of physical phenomena. The square root of 2 is irrational, yet it appears in various mathematical models and physical phenomena. History is replete with examples of seemingly abstract or "useless" mathematical concepts later finding scientific applications. This demonstrates the danger of prematurely dismissing mathematical structures as ontologically irrelevant in their case. 10 is just as non-existent as $\aleph_0$, as they are both abstract objects, regardless of how one number can be ascribed to physical objects, while the other cannot.

The strength mathematics has in the case of indispensability does not necessarily lie on its supposed existence, but on its explanatory power, which should not determine ontological rights. This is where I will potentially dismantle such power, or at least reveal its flaws in terms of its usage in empirical science.

4.2.1. *Newtonian Cosmology*

In 1687, Sir Isaac Newton presented a remarkable new model of the universe in "*Philosophiæ Naturalis Principia Mathematica*," or simply, "*Principia*," a three-volume book which signaled a paradigm shift and became the foundation of physics which succeeded it.

Newtonian Cosmology is principally concerned with the investigation of the aggregate gravitational force manifested by a specified test particle at arbitrary positions within the cosmos. Scientists sought to resolve this problem through the amalgamation of Newton's law of gravitation, Poisson's equation, and contemplations of symmetry and gravitational potential. However, the employment of this method reveals discernible incongruities. While Newtonian Cosmology establishes a fundamental paradigm for comprehending expansive cosmic dynamics grounded in Newtonian principles, its practical implementation is confronted with incongruities, notably in the examination of gravitational forces on a cosmic scale.

There are two primary types of contradictions emerging from this theory. The first arises when the force on a test particle is simultaneously identified as X and Y , where $X \neq Y$. However, the crux of mathematical interest lies in the second type of contradiction, wherein a unique gravitational force on a test mass is asserted to exist, while simultaneously not being the case. This is split into two parts: P and $\neq P$.²⁹

Analyzing the implications of (a) Newton's three laws of motion, (b) the inverse square law of gravitation, and (c) the isotropic and homogeneous distribution of matter in infinite Euclidean space, the narrative concludes that the net force on a test mass is undetermined. This assertion, however, clashes

²⁹ See Vickers 2013 for further reading.

with Newtonian laws, which posit (d) a determinate force on a body exists all the time.³⁰ The source of the contradiction is traced to the misinterpretation of an indeterminate infinite sum, a conceptual error exploited by early scientists enamored with Newtonian Cosmology.³¹ The resolution to this contradiction is attributed to Augustin-Louis Cauchy, who demonstrated that, in the face of an indeterminate sum, the correct approach is to acknowledge the absence of a solution.

To further elaborate this contradiction, consider Newton's first law: 'a body at rest stays at rest and a body at motion stays in motion (acceleration),' directly implying that there is *always* a determinate force on a body. We have the four propositions, (a) to (d), where (d) leads to the second type of contradiction.

A determinate force is consistently applicable to any physical body, whether it possesses substance or is devoid thereof. The incorporation of factor (d) then does not constitute the introduction of a novel assumption; instead, it seamlessly aligns with the existing premises denoted as (a). The purported contradiction of indeterminacy is intended to derive from the conjunction of (a), (b), and (c). A crucial distinction emerges at this juncture. While the combination of (b) and (c) results in an indeterminate infinite sum, preventing a definitive answer to the question "*what is the force?*", it remains an open question whether this circumstance necessitates the inference that there exists no singular gravitational force acting upon a test mass. Thus, there are two inferences which can be made:

³⁰ The 4 propositions stated here are, for better description:

- a) Newton's three laws of motion;
- b) Newton's law of gravitational attraction—the force of gravity $\mathbf{F}_i$ on a test body m_t at $\mathbf{r}$ due to another body m_i at $\mathbf{r}_i$ is given by $\mathbf{F}_i = G \frac{m_t m_i}{|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}|^3} \mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}$;
- c) Matter in the universe is distributed homogeneously (when viewed on a large enough scale) in an infinite Euclidean space; and
- d) There is a unique gravitational force on a test mass fixed by (b) and (c).

³¹ In the context of indeterminate sums and the discussion about the net gravitational force on a test mass in Newtonian Cosmology, the concept of an indeterminate sum refers to a series whose terms do not converge to a definite value.

1. Conclude that a solution not having been found is indicated by indeterminacy, or
2. Deduce that indeterminacy implies the non-existence of a solution.

We then adopt the stronger inference, no. 2, as centuries of mathematics has revealed that no. 1 is the wrong way to think about indeterminate sums. No. 2 [(b), (c), and (2)] can be expressed as:

$$\forall 1 \in \mathfrak{R}^3, \sum_i \mathbf{F}_i \neq 1$$

Expressing (d) and (b) mathematically, we find ourselves with three equalities which illustrate the contradiction:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \exists k \in \mathfrak{R}^3, k = \mathbf{F}_{net} & \mathbf{F}_{net} = \sum_i \mathbf{F}_i & \forall 1 \in \mathfrak{R}^3, \sum_i \mathbf{F}_i \neq 1 \\ (d) & (b) & (b),(c),(2) \end{array}$$

From the substitutivity of identicals we can then write,

$$\exists k \in \mathfrak{R}^3, \forall 1 \in \mathfrak{R}^3, k \neq 1.$$

Failure to adhere to this principle is characterized as a metaphysical error, asserting that scientists, by employing incorrect mathematics, have inadvertently introduced inconsistencies into their metaphysical understanding of cosmic forces. This shows that in defense of indispensability, its proponents set science up to the errors and limitations of mathematics.³²

³² In the off-chance that you still find my critique of Newtonian Cosmology to be trivial to the debate to prove that mathematics is dispensable, then here I provide further enumerated discussion of some of the other limitations of mathematics:

- I. The self-consistency of the Standard Model of particle physics, which describes 3 of the 4 fundamental forces—electromagnetic, weak & strong interactions, excluding gravitational—has not been mathematically proven. Time and time again, scientists have attempted to extend the Standard Model into a Theory of Everything; attempts which have failed. Furthermore, the Model is inelegant as it requires arbitrary and unrelated constants in order to work, and it is also inconsistent with the cosmological Lambda-CDM (cold dark matter) model.
- II. The foundations of mathematics are too convoluted, circular, and inelegant to assume that it is by and large the language of the universe. Case in point: Gödel's

4.2.2. Field's Nominalization Project

To crystallize my second assertion, we will turn to Field's nominalization project, which aims to remove all reference to and quantification over mathematical objects—from which will bring us to Newton once again. Field has nominalized one important scientific theory: Newtonian Gravitational Theory (NGT).

NGT describes the physical world by attributing numerical values, such as mass and distance, to points in space-time. The framework employs a mathematical coordinate system to represent space-time, and statements like "The mass of a is 10kg" are construed as signifying the existence of a mass-in-kilograms function, denoted as f , mapping from a domain of concrete objects (C) to real numbers ($\mathbb{R}$), with $f(a)$ equal to 10. In contrast, Field's theory (henceforth FGT) articulates the concrete domain directly, utilizing comparative language.

Notably, distance claims incorporate primitive relations such as " y Bet xz ," denoting that y is between x and z , " x Simul y ," indicating simultaneity between x and y , and " xy Cong zw ," signifying congruence of distance from x to y and from z to w . Similarly, mass claims employ mass-betweenness and mass-congruence relations. Field ingeniously constructs a scientific theory capable of characterizing space-time and its properties without resorting to the quantification of mathematical objects.

Field's representation theorem then demonstrates that the concrete domain, encapsulated by FGT through the utilization of comparative predicates (depicting a space-time imbued with mass-density and gravitational attributes), shares identical structural features with the abstract

incompleteness theorem, which states that any effectively generated theory capable of expressing elementary arithmetic cannot be both *consistent* and *complete*. Consider the statement $P' =$ "This sentence cannot be proved in S ."

- a. If P' is false, then P' can be proved in S (which means you can prove false statements in S , therefore it is inconsistent).
- b. If P' is true, then P' cannot be proved inside S (it is incomplete; there are statements about S that can't be proved inside S).

mathematical model of space-time endowed with mass-density and gravitational properties as stipulated by NGT.

The foundation of empirical science is conceptual, rather than mathematical. The explanatory power of mathematics does not surpass that of other descriptive methods in science.

At the very least, *in principle*, we are able to prove that mathematics is dispensable to the description of physical phenomena, especially when attractiveness is retained in the absence of reference to mathematical objects—and in the case of this paper, in physics. It is still important to note that this claim does not necessarily recommend that we completely disregard the application of mathematics in empirical science, especially when it has proven itself useful. An instrumentalist approach is in order.

Referencing Mary Leng, all it takes for a given mathematically imbued scientific theory or explanation to be a good one is for the concrete world to be intrinsically as it needs to be in order for that theory or explanation to be consistent, and that mathematical entities need not exist in order for this to be the case.³³ We cannot logically assume that mathematics in its entirety, remains consistent with the functions of the physical world; it just so happens that math is unreasonably effective in performing this role, all while having independent rules of its own that do not have real-life counterparts. As we do not have a concrete answer to what is clearly an enigma, the limits of this paper remain within the bounds of our relationship with mathematics.

4.3. *Third Claim: Religionism*

*In college I had to take calculus. I loved it! But nobody explained the big picture to me. How is it possible that the derivative of $\sin(x)$ ends up being exactly $\cos(x)$? What are the odds of that happening? The area under the curve is the opposite of the slope of a tangent line. How could that be? Why is nobody flabbergasted about this? Did I miss something?*³⁴

³³ Leng, Mary. "Revolutionary Fictionalism: A Call to Arms." *Philosophia Mathematica* 13 (2005): 277–293.

³⁴ Radulović, Dragan. *Why Does Math Work ... If It's Not Real? Episodes in Unreasonable Effectiveness*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2023. doi: 10.1017/9781009051774.

The illusory truth-value that composes a significant part of the general attitude toward mathematics is something that can be attributed to its unreasonable effectiveness. There seems to be an unspoken acceptance of ontological commitment when learning about math; it is something largely unquestioned. This attitude is what feeds the most commonplace debate within the realm of mathematical philosophy—is math discovered *or* invented? Finally, this brings us to the defense of the THIRD OF THE CENTRAL CLAIMS: the truth-value of mathematics is falsely perceived and is paradigmatic in nature. This perception is what I refer to as *mathematical religionism*.

Elaborating on the false perception of the truth-value of mathematics, I return to Wigner and unreasonable effectiveness. This specific characteristic of mathematics, of which many credit their religionist attitude, can be exemplified by what Galileo Galilei in his book, “The Assayer”:

*[The universe] cannot be read until we have learnt the language and become familiar with the characters in which it is written. It is written in mathematical language, and the letters are triangles, circles and other geometrical figures, without which means it is humanly impossible to comprehend a single word.*³⁵

The quotation has gained prominence as a misunderstood argument positing a connection between human beings and the omniscient and omnipresent God, suggesting that our capacity for mathematical reasoning positions us as beings closest to the divine. According to this perspective, mathematics serves as the divine language that we have unveiled.

I shall emphasize that I do not purport that these false beliefs that consequentially place mathematics on such a high pedestal to be wild claims that were deduced out of thin air. We can take one of the laws of mathematical logic, $(P \wedge Q \vee R) \Leftrightarrow (P \wedge Q \vee P \wedge R)$ —this statement of logic is nothing but a mere reflection, a direct manifestation of the geometric distributive property, $A(B + C) = AB + AC$. Even the branch of math concerned with the very abstractions of the human mind cannot escape the

³⁵ Galilei, Galileo. "The Assayer." In *Discoveries and Opinions of Galileo*, edited by Stillman Drake, 171. Doubleday, 1957. (Original work published in 1623.)

grip of geometry, the branch which binds all of mathematics together in a grand design. Probability, statistics, and real analysis for instance, are all based on axioms that essentially are mere geometric rules.

With math being so inescapable, it is only within human nature to have the tendency to draw conclusions as to mathematics having a ‘divine’ or ontologically strong nature.

Although, very few people are aware, it is noteworthy that a substantial majority of active mathematicians do not purposefully strive for the practical utility or applicability of mathematics. For the most part, mathematicians predominantly engage in exploratory and recreational endeavors with equations and theorems, often without explicit consideration of potential real-world applications stemming from their mathematical pursuits. This furthers the case for unreasonable effectiveness—applications often end up in unpredictable manners and circumstances, as I have illustrated.

Nevertheless, having had discussed the ontology of mathematics, it becomes evident why perspectives on the field tend to align with a religio-mathematical stance. Various factors contribute to this orientation, ranging from principled considerations to political dynamics: the relationship of math and empirical science, its intricacies, effectiveness, versatility, its seemingly objective nature (stemming from its axiomatic, logical system), *math-phobia*, and even how math education is handled in different countries. It is necessary then for us to recognize and reshape such an attitude, especially when considering the epistemological dimension of the issue. We cannot possibly rely in empirical science for knowledge and ensure its truth-value if we take one of its tools for granted, even at a higher position than it deserves— we are required a critical examination of its mathematical foundations to avoid reducing it to unquestioned dogma.

For one, humans see what they look for. Pattern recognition is a widely recognized evolutionary trait we have cultivated, a cognitive process that matches information from a stimulus with information retrieved from

memory.³⁶ There are nontrivial physical phenomena, such as Galileo's law of falling bodies and the uncertainty principle of quantum mechanics following the properties of Fourier integrals and time invariance assumptions, which arose from mathematical tools employed and not the intrinsic properties of physical reality.

Mathematically imbued scientific theories such as quantum field theory derive from scientific inquiries that specifically aim to approach aspects of the universe which can be explained by mathematics. Instances then come up where mathematics precedes the scientific method. Furthermore, humans often create or select mathematics on an ad hoc basis, and the available mathematical frameworks may not always be universally applicable or pre-existing. Oftentimes, physicists shelve inquiries which cannot be answered through available mathematics, going under the impression that they can simply be answered by math in the future.

To assert that the universe can be completely explained via mathematics amounts to an act of faith. Until there is a complete mathematical description of the universe in all its glory, the idea that the universe has inherent mathematical characteristics and properties is unfounded. Here, we see how the fallacious argument of math being the universal language crumbles under scrutiny. Even straight lines, the key component of linearity, which itself is among the primary themes of all of mathematics, find no direct correspondence in our physical world. Evolution has simply primed human beings to think mathematically, thus leading us to resort to such an approach in order to comprehend the world around us.

Mathematics is merely a medium from which we can perceive reality that exists independent of us. Instead of it being the divine matter which governs the universe, its dominion over human abstractions only prove that our experience of 'reality' will always be subjected to socially-constructed

³⁶ Eysenck, M. W., & Keane, M. T. (2003). *Cognitive Psychology: A Student's Handbook* (4th ed.). Hove; Philadelphia; New York: Taylor & Francis. ISBN 9780863775512. OCLC 894210185.

interpretations. We attempt to get closer and closer to reality, only to never reach it.

Now, finally, what does it mean for mathematics to be paradigmatic? We turn to Thomas Kuhn. Kuhn delineates a trajectory that begins with Normal Science, where scientists operate within an accepted paradigm, engaging in routine problem-solving to extend prevailing theories. Progression in research eventually gives rise to anomalies—unexpected findings challenging the existing framework—marking the onset of a Crisis. This Crisis prompts Revolutionary Science, characterized by the exploration of alternative theories to address anomalies, culminating in a Paradigm Shift that transforms the foundational assumptions of the discipline. The adoption of a new paradigm initiates a return to Normal Science within the updated framework.³⁷

Within mathematics, paradigms are embodied in established theories, axioms, and mathematical structures embraced by mathematicians. Euclidean geometry, as an enduring paradigm, illustrates this concept, providing a foundational framework for spatial understanding and serving as a cognitive structure for problem-solving akin to the Normal Science phase. However, the stability of mathematical paradigms faces disruption when anomalies emerge—instances where mathematical tools or frameworks fail in empirical contexts. Analogous to the Crisis phase, these anomalies prompt mathematicians to reassess established paradigms and explore alternative mathematical structures, mirroring the introduction of non-Euclidean geometries in response to challenges posed by anomalies in Euclidean geometry. In mathematics, the Crisis phase arises when empirical phenomena necessitate a departure from established paradigms.

However, viewing mathematics in the broader context of empirical science and the general populace, it becomes clear that the framework is enjoying its Normal Science phase. This implies that mathematics, as the established paradigm from which science operates, is primarily shielded from skepticism—that is, until the limitations of mathematics are reached by the

³⁷ Kuhn, Thomas S. *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1962.

scope of scientific inquiry, which in a handful of situations, have been the case. Mathematics is paradigmatic in an enduring way which propagates religionism.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS, SUMMARY, & CONCLUSION

To philosophers who intend to respond to and refute my claims—the heavy burden of justifying ontological commitment despite the incongruence of mathematics to physical reality, and the reality which it fundamentally lacks, is a burden you must carry. To philosophers who intend to extend the ideas found on this essay, there are aspects to my arguments which are lacking and which I am unaware of.

To the reader, we ought to bifurcate the truth-values of empirical science and mathematics, despite them being intertwined in operation. Regardless of our proximity to scientific and mathematical practice, there should be a conscious understanding of mathematical nature and to which extent we should maintain ontological commitment to knowledge-producing systems, especially when the system references abstract objects that harbor no physical correspondence.

Our attitude towards mathematics ought to be instrumentalist—useful fictions which do not relate to an objective truth. This is especially true to scientists and mathematicians who often do not care enough to consider the philosophical dimension of their fields. After all, mathematics is not only fundamentally false (as abstract objects do not exist) and dispensable to empirical science, but it is also seen in a skewed, zealous, and divine—*religionist*—light; in direct contradiction with what people think of math: objectively true, logical, and devoid of the '*weaknesses*' of human emotions. It is ironic that, ultimately, mathematics remains to be among the things which make us human.

Φ

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